

Sophytes and the Mirage of an ‘Indian’ Weight Standard

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For more than 150 years numismatic scholarship postulated that a coinage associated with Sophytes was struck on an ‘Indian’ weight standard. Despite mounting evidence to the contrary, this evolved into an enduring mirage, accompanied by an added dimension of complexity, one that posited that the coinage was struck simultaneously on two weight standards, Attic and ‘Indian.’ This mirage, and its associated complexity is dispersed completely by a comprehensive metrological analysis of 957 coins across seven silver denominations in the coinage of Sophytes, and his predecessor Andragoras, struck in Parthia during the period 250s-238 BC. It confirms that eleven series of issues in the coinage constitute a single currency system, an epichoric coinage that was systematically weight adjusted based on a reduced Attic weight standard tetradrachm of 17.00 grams, with an increased component seigniorage, up to fifteen percent, applied to the smaller denominations. This metrology is reflective of its origin in the mid 3rd century BC.

For the better part of a century numismatic wisdom held that an imitative Athenian coinage attributed to Bactria, plus the associated Athena/eagle coinage, and that of helmeted male head/cockle bearing the legend ΣΩΦΥΤΟΥ (of Sophytos¹) was struck on two weight standards; the Attic standard for tetradrachms some didrachms and drachms, while another component of the didrachms, plus the majority of the drachms and all the fractions were considered to have been struck on an Indian weight standard.² This had its origin in 1866 with the assumption by Sir Alexander Cunningham that the Sophytes drachm that had come into his possession with a weight of 58.25 grains (3.77 grams) was struck by the Indian prince named Σοπειθης (Sopeithes) mentioned in the ancient sources, a minor dynast in the Punjab who submitted to Alexander the Great.³ With this association he then concluded that the coin must have been struck on an Indian weight standard, although he did concede that the coin might also have been struck on a light Attic standard,⁴ a point that with few exceptions⁵ was ignored by generations of subsequent scholars.

Cunningham estimated the weight of the most basic unit of Indian weight measurement, the *ratti* seed, to be 1.83 grains (0.118582 grams) based on his calculation of the average weight of the seed of *Abrus precatorius*.⁶ From this he deduced the weight of what was to become known as the

¹ Given the long-standing numismatic convention in the use of the name Sophytes, I have retained this form rather than referring to Sophytos.

² Cunningham (1866); Head (1906); Mitchiner (1975): 5, table I(c) and 9; Boppearachchi (1996); Boppearachchi (1998).

³ Strabo *Geography* 15.1.30; Diodorus *Bibliotheca historica* 17.91-93; Arrian *Anabasis* 6.2.2 and Cunningham (1866). The name Sophytes was derived from Cunningham’s desire to equate the legend ΣΩΦΥΤΟΥ with the individual named Σοπειθης (Sopeithes) in the ancient sources, which as noted by Whitehead (1943): 63-65 was a false etymology. The correct transliteration is most certainly Sophytos.

⁴ Cunningham (1866): 230.

⁵ Whitehead (1943): 62, 71 and 74; Rapson (1922): 61, 388, and 462-3. Both considered the Sophytes drachm to be that of a light Attic weight standard.

⁶ Cunningham (1866): 230; Cunningham (1891): 44 unaccompanied by detail of the sampling employed in this determination, which has since proved to be an overestimate; refer Tye (2020). The *ratti* seed is a natural product, the weight of which varies significantly by geography and season. It is apparent that there is little statistical validity in efforts to determine the weight of the historical *ratti*, a notional unit of weight, by the measurement of a small, geographically, and seasonally constrained, present day sample of actual seeds. Rather, the weights of coins themselves are the best guide to the exact weight of the notional *ratti*.

Magadha-Mauryan *karshapana* (32 *rattis*) must have been 58.56 grains (3.79 grams)⁷ very close to the weight of his Sophytes drachm. This was a convenient if not remarkable coincidence, which taken at face value supported his argument for the association of the coin with Sopeithes of the ancient sources. However, this argument was flawed not only in terms of the notional weight of the *ratti* seed,⁸ but also with respect to the weight standard applicable to Northwest India at the time of the Macedonian campaign through the Indus Valley. Cunningham overlooked the fact that in the time of Sopeithes the Pre-Mauryan weight standard applicable to the punch-marked silver coinage struck in northwest India, including the Indus Valley, was that of the silver *shatamana*, with a weight of 11.66 grams.⁹ In the *shatamana* system no denomination approximated that of a drachm of 3.77 grams. Only in the decades after the conquest of the Punjab in 317 BC¹⁰ by Chandragupta Maurya did the Magadha-Mauryan *karshapana* weight standard (3.42 grams)¹¹ spread from the eastern state of Magadha throughout the Mauryan Empire, and thus into northwest India.

Although Cunningham's speculation of an Indian weight standard proved to be chronologically and metrologically flawed, this laid the foundation of an enduring mirage, the vision of an Indian weight standard in the coinage of Sophytes. This initiated a chain of numismatic speculation that developed with greater complexity for the better part of 150 years; one that led 20th century numismatists to assert that coinage was struck contemporaneously north of the Hindu Kush on both Attic and Indian weight standards, firstly by Sophytes, and subsequently Seleukos I and Antiochos I during the coregency (294-281 BC).¹² Based on a meagre sample, Mitchiner presented a metrological summary of the so called Indian weight standard component of this coinage, from which he concluded that it was based on a tetradrachm of 14.0 grams, and thus a drachm of 3.5 grams.¹³ Although of no statistical validity, this was accepted at face value by many numismatists.¹⁴ Critically, the total sample of the owl, eagle, and cockerel (Sophytes) emissions in the drachm denomination consisted of only 14 coins and exhibited a wide spread of weights in a flat distribution across the weight range 3.1-3.7 grams. Demonstrably, the sample was of insufficient size and quality to define the weight to which the Sophytes drachm was adjusted. Recently, the Indian origin of this weight standard has been reasserted by some scholars,¹⁵ unsupported by comprehensive and comparative metrological analysis. In all cases these studies overlook the now well-established fact that the Magadha-Mauryan *karshapana* which circulated in northwest India during the Mauryan period was adjusted to a weight standard of 3.4 grams.¹⁶

⁷ This has since proved to be an incorrect determination of the Magadha-Mauryan *karshapana* standard, which still persists in some numismatic literature to the present-day e.g. Hoover (2013): lxxxi-lxxxii. In contrast, Gupta and Hardaker (2014): 32 and 86, established empirically that the Magadha-Mauryan *karshapana* was adjusted to a weight of c. 3.40 grams (giving a notional *ratti* weight of 0.10625g), while Tye (2020) derives a *karshapana* weight of 3.426 grams (giving a notional *ratti* of 0.107g). Almost certainly, by the time of the *karshapana* the *ratti* was a notional weight rather than one measured using actual seeds: Joe Cribb (pers. comm. via email dated 18 August 2001).

⁸ Cunningham's weight determination proved to be an overestimate, a point noted by Whitehead (1943): 63, subsequently supported by the recent analysis of Gupta and Hardaker (2014): 32 and 86, and Tye (2020): 3.

⁹ Hoover (2013): lxxxii.

¹⁰ Grainger(2007): 101 citing Raychauduri (1996): 234-40 and 591-3.

¹¹ Gupta and Hardaker (2014): 32 and 86; Tye (2020): 3.

¹² Newell (1938): 233-234; Bopearachchi (2015): 86; Kriti (2016): 19-81.

¹³ Mitchiner (1975): 5, table I(c), and 9.

¹⁴ Bopearachchi (1996); Bopearachchi (1998): preface to the Pre-Seleucid coins of Bactria in SNG ANS Part 9; Bopearachchi (1999); 79; Hoover (2013): 3-6.

¹⁵ Bordeaux (2021): 85-88; Jansari (2018): 83-86.

¹⁶ Gupta and Hardaker (2014): 32 and 86.

In 2019, I published a study of the control linked imitative Athenian owl, eagle, and cockerel (Sophytes) issues, analysed as a single currency system, with the weight adjustment of each of seven denominations estimated from a sample 300 coins assembled in 2017.¹⁷ This demonstrated that the imitative owl (Series 1 and 2), eagle (Series 3, 4 and 5), and cockerel (Series 7 and 8) emissions previously attributed to Bactria are extensively linked by style, coin fabric, mint controls, and metrology, to those in the name of Andragoras (Series 6), the satrap of Parthia.¹⁸ Including three minor issues from a possible secondary mint (Series 9-11), the coinage system consisted of eleven typological series in seven silver denominations struck prior to the conquest of the province of Parthia by Arsaces in 238 BC (Figure 1). Metrological analysis concluded that the coinage was based on a reduced Attic weight standard tetradrachm with an increasing weight deficit, and thus fiduciary component of value attached, to the smaller denominations. It invalidated the proposition that the didrachms and drachms were struck on two weight standards, while the presence of a number of series with coincident weight distributions in each denomination served to demonstrate that all were part of the same currency system.

In recent years more than 600 previously unseen specimens of the coinage entered numismatic trade, tripling the corpus of this once rare coinage.¹⁹ This enlarged sample of the coinage has confirmed the typological framework, and increased the coherency of the mint control links between the various series.²⁰ It has considerably increased the sample size across all denominations, including a large number of exceptionally well preserved and unworn coins, sufficient to merit a new metrological evaluation.

An empirical approach to the determination of the weight adjustment of each denomination in the coinage is employed in this study. This ignores speculations regarding an Indian weight standard and its possible origins. It relies on the observed weight distributions of the various denominations to define the system of weight adjustment employed in the coinage. The results are then compared to other contemporary Hellenistic coinages, and the Indian Magadha-Mauryan *karshapana* that circulated throughout the Indus Valley under Chandragupta Maurya and his successors. The weight data was assembled by series from previously published data and recent numismatic sales.²¹ The sample was screened for multiple sales of the same specimen in order to avoid duplication of entries in the data set. Where identified, incorrectly recorded weights were corrected.²² The metrics of the weight distribution for the sample of each of the component series in each denomination are presented in Table 1, with the total sample illustrated in a histogram on Figure 2. Histograms of the weights in each series and the total sample in each denomination are presented in Figures 3-7.

¹⁷ Taylor (2019).

¹⁸ Taylor (forthcoming 2022): table 1; Taylor (2019).

¹⁹ Taylor (2020): 54, footnote 3 for the background to this new material, which undoubtedly represents the content of a substantial hoard introduced into numismatic trade, referred to as the Andragoras-Sophytes Group in Roma Numismatics (2017): 106.

²⁰ Taylor (2020); Taylor (2021); Taylor (2022).

²¹ Published data sources: Cunningham (1866); Nicolet-Pierre (1973); Mitchiner (1975); Nicolet-Pierre and Amandry (1990); Bopearachchi (1996); Bopearachchi (1998); Bopearachchi (1999); Bopearachchi (2015); Jansari (2018); Taylor (2019). Numismatic sales data sourced from: www.romanumismatics.com, www.acsearch.info and www.sixbid.com prior to 1 December 2021.

²² This included the correction of the weight of Taylor (2019) catalogue entry 201 from 1.49 grams to 1.13 grams, thus eliminating what was inferred to be a Series 4 hemidrachm from the sequence. Another significant correction was to the weight of a Series 2 didrachm, SNG ANS 4, for which both the accession number and weight were incorrectly recorded in the SNG where it was incorrectly identified as ANS 1995.51.254 with an anomalously heavy weight of 9.41 grams. In the ANS MANTIS database this coin is recorded under accession no.1995.51.284 with a weight of 6.41 grams.

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		Mint A (Hekatompylos?)					
<i>Series</i>		Series 1		Series 2		Series 3	
<i>Iconography</i>		Athena/owl		Athena/owl		Athena/eagle	
<i>Denomination</i>		Tetradrachm, didrachm, drachm, hemidrachm		Tetradrachm, didrachm, drachm, hemidrachm		Drachm, hemidrachm	
<i>Series</i>		Series 4		Series 5		Series 6	
<i>Iconography</i>		Athena/owl		Tyche/Eagle		Tyche/standing Athena	
<i>Denomination</i>		Diobol, trihemiobol		Obol		Tetradrachm	
<i>Series</i>		Series 7		Series 7		Series 8	
<i>Iconography</i>		Athena/cockrel		Athena/cockrel		Sophytes/cockrel	
<i>Denomination</i>		Tetradrachm		Diobol, trihemiobol, obol		Tetradrachm, didrachm, drachm, hemidrachm, obol	
		Mint B (military campaign mint?)					
<i>Series</i>		Series 9		Series 10		Series 11	
<i>Iconography</i>		Kalathos/double bodied owl		Athena/eagle		Sophytes/cockrel	
<i>Denomination</i>		Trihemiobol		Drachm		Trihemiobol, obol	

Figure 1. Silver coinage of Andragoras and Sophytes (c. 250s-238 BC). (coin images are not to scale)

Table 1. Metrological data summary.

	No. of coins	Weight Range (g)	Mean (g)	Median (g)	Modal Class (g)	σ (g)
<i>Tetradrachms</i>						
Series 1 (Athena/owl)	77	14.74 - 17.33	16.61	16.69	16.50 - 16.59	0.46
Series 2 (Athena/owl)	170	15.49 - 17.25	16.77	16.83	16.80 - 16.89	0.31
Series 6 (Andragoras)	45	15.32 - 17.32	16.77	16.83	16.70 - 16.79	0.39
Series 7 & 8 (Sophytes)	21	15.75 - 17.20	16.91	16.97	16.90 - 16.99	0.29
	313	14.74 - 17.33	16.74	16.82	16.90 - 16.99	0.37
<i>Didrachms</i>						
Series 1 (Athena/owl)	8	7.50 - 8.32	7.95	7.94	-	0.34
Series 2 (Athena/owl)	195	6.12 - 8.59	7.91	8.01	8.00 - 8.09	0.31
Series 8 (Sophytes)	20	7.40 - 8.09	7.95	8.00	8.00 - 8.09	0.16
	223	6.12 - 8.59	7.92	8.00	8.00 - 8.09	0.30
<i>Drachms</i>						
Series 1 (Athena/owl)	18	3.41 - 3.90	3.69	3.73	3.70 - 3.79	0.15
Series 2 (Athena/owl)	11	3.22 - 4.28	3.71	3.71	3.60 - 3.69	0.29
Series 3 (Athena/eagle)	124	2.42 - 3.75	3.44	3.50	3.50 - 3.59	0.22
Series 8 (Sophytes)	71	3.03 - 4.15	3.57	3.61	3.50 - 3.59	0.23
Series 10 (Athena/eagle)	2	3.34 - 3.51	3.43	3.43	-	0.12
	226	2.42 - 4.28	3.51	3.53	3.50 - 3.59	0.24
<i>Hemidrachms</i>						
Series 1 (Athena/owl)	12	1.44 - 2.03	1.75	1.80	1.80 - 1.89	0.22
Series 2 (Athena/owl)	33	1.46 - 1.86	1.69	1.68	1.60 - 1.69	0.10
Series 3 (Athena/eagle)	31	1.29 - 1.81	1.65	1.68	1.70 - 1.79	0.13
Series 8 (Sophytes)	13	1.21 - 1.84	1.60	1.61	1.70 - 1.79	0.20
	89	1.21 - 2.03	1.67	1.68	1.60 - 1.69	0.15
<i>Diobols</i>						
Series 4 (Zeus/Eagle)	27	0.93 - 1.49	1.09	1.08	1.00 - 1.09	0.11
Series 7 (Athena/cock)	17	0.95 - 1.18	1.08	1.09	1.10 - 1.19	0.06
	44	0.93 - 1.49	1.09	1.08	1.00 - 1.09	0.09
<i>Trihemibols</i>						
Series 4 (Zeus/Eagle)	6	0.70 - 0.81	0.74	0.72	0.70 - 0.79	0.05

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Series 7 (Athena/cock)	4	0.70 - 0.89	0.83	0.87	-	0.09
Series 9 (Kalathos/owl)	13	0.67 - 1.06	0.82	0.80	0.80 - 0.89	0.11
Series 11 (Head/cock)	1	0.74	0.74	-	-	-
	24	0.67 - 1.06	0.80	0.79	0.70 - 0.79	0.10

Obols

Series 5 (Tyche/eagle)	15	0.37 - 0.62	0.49	0.50	0.50 - 0.59	0.07
Series 7 (Athena/cock)	3	0.47 - 0.60	0.56	0.60	-	0.08
Series 8 (Sophytes/cock)	19	0.35 - 0.66	0.50	0.51	0.50 - 0.59	0.08
Series 11 (Head/cock)	1	0.58 - 0.58	0.58	-	-	-
	38	0.35 - 0.66	0.50	0.51	0.50 - 0.59	0.08

Figure 2. Histogram of weights. (0.10 gram intervals, discontinuous horizontal axis)

The establishment of the weight standard to which an ancient Greek coinage was struck is not a straightforward outcome of statistical analysis.²³ Numerous factors must be considered including the size and statistical validity of the sample, the varying state of wear of coins in the sample, and the precision with which weight adjustment was undertaken in the mint. Mints tended towards

²³ Mørkholm (1991): 7-11.

slightly underweight striking against the nominal weight standard for a denomination, thus benefiting from seigniorage, the difference between the face value of a coin and the lesser value of its metal content. Depending on the degree of seigniorage, this would offset the cost of mintage, and might even generate a profit. Varying precision and consistency in the adjustment process could result in the striking of overweight or underweight coins, removed from the targeted weight. In these aberrant adjustments overweight coins were more likely to be culled and remelted due to the excess precious metal value, while the underweight coins were less likely to receive such attention, contributing to a skew in the weight distribution towards lower weights.

In addition to these considerations, the nature of the weight adjustment process has bearing on the merits of various statistical measures as an indicator of weight adjustment in a coinage. The adjustment of the weight of metal in each flan to a specific weight prior to striking (*al pezzo* adjustment) results in a relatively tight distribution of coin weights with the most frequently encountered weight (the statistical mode) aligned closely to the mint's target weight for the emission. Alternatively, the mintage of a specific number of coins per weight of metal in a batch process with little regard for the weight of individual coins (e.g. *al marco* adjustment) results in a distribution of weights in which the statistical mean is representative of the mint's target weight for the issue.²⁴ Wear and poor preservation will act to negatively influence the mean and flatten the mode in a sample of ancient coins. Regardless of the type of adjustment the weight of any denomination will typically be slightly less than the nominal weight standard due to seigniorage, other than in rare instances of a gratuitous coinage.²⁵ The target weights to which coins of various denominations were adjusted defines a system of adjustment, while the weight of largest denomination, allowing for seigniorage, is usually considered to define the nominal weight standard to which the coinage was struck. The distinction between the weight adjustment targets expressed in a coinage system and the nominal weight standard of the coinage is often overlooked, and a potential source of confusion.

In the sample of 957 coins the heavier end of the weight distribution in each denomination approximates a normal distribution (Figure 2). Together with the absence of any of the physical markers associated with *al marco* adjustment, this suggests that the coinage was adjusted *al pezzo*, the usual practice in early Hellenistic coinage. The long tail of lower weights in each weight distribution is in large part the result of the presence of coins in varying states of wear and preservation. Ideally, only the weights of uncirculated coins would be the basis of the weight determination for each denomination. Therefore, the lowest weights in the sample that are the result of wear, damage, corrosion, and other post-mintage factors should be removed from the consideration. Table 2 presents the metrics of a truncated distribution that results.²⁶ This yields a near normal (Gaussian) weight distribution for each denomination in which the mean, median and modal weights are closely aligned in a distribution with a modest standard deviation compared to that of the raw sample. The metrics of the truncated sample more closely (though not precisely) reflect the weight distribution of the coinage as struck.

²⁴ Stannard (2011).

²⁵ In a gratuitous coinage the issuing authority bore the full cost of mintage.

²⁶ In this approach the weights of those coins more than one standard deviation below the mean have been removed. This is roughly equivalent to two standard deviations from the mean of the unworn, well preserved larger denomination coins c.f. the change in σ between Tables 1 and 2.

Table 2: Truncated sample.

Denomination	No. of coins	Range (g)	Mean (g)	Median (g)	Modal Class (g)	σ (g)
Tetradrachm	270	16.38 - 17.33	16.85	16.82	16.90 - 16.99	0.21
Didrachm	199	7.59 - 8.59	8.00	8.02	8.00 - 8.09	0.14
Drachm	198	3.30 - 4.28	3.57	3.55	3.50 - 3.59	0.16
Hemidrachm	79	1.52 - 2.03	1.71	1.72	1.60 - 1.69	0.10
Diobol	39	1.00 - 1.49	1.10	1.09	1.00 - 1.09	0.08
Trihemiobol	23	0.70 - 1.06	0.80	0.80	0.70 - 0.79	0.09
Obol	30	0.43 - 0.66	0.53	0.51	0.50 - 0.59	0.05

The tetradrachm sample consists of imitative Athenian owls (Series 1 and 2), plus issues struck in the name of Andragoras (Series 6) and Sophytes (Series 7 and 8). The weight distribution of each of the component series is similar to that of the others, while a modal peak is evident across two adjacent weight classes, 16.80-16.89 and 16.90-16.99 grams, with the latter division defining the statistical modal class by the margin of a single coin (Figure 3). Forty percent of the sample falls in the range 16.80-16.99 grams, which includes the mean, median and modal weights (Table 2). Based on the weight distribution the best estimate of the weight to which the tetradrachm flans were adjusted is 16.90 grams, with an associated uncertainty of ± 0.10 grams.²⁷ This weight adjustment coincides with that of the tetradrachms of Seleukos II and Antiochos III struck at Antioch; a reduced Attic weight standard with nominal tetradrachm weight of 17.00 grams that was the norm throughout the Seleukid realm during the 3rd century BC.²⁸ The tetradrachm sample in the 2019 study consisted of only 74 coins, less than one quarter of the current sample, and yielded a broad weight distribution with a weakly defined mode around 16.80 grams that was inferred to be the weight adjustment for the denomination.²⁹ The considerably increased sample size provides a more robust definition of the weight adjustment of the tetradrachm due to the inclusion in the sample of a relatively high percentage of well-preserved and unworn coins in recent commerce.

The didrachm sample is most informative of the answer to the question of whether dual weight standards exists in the coinage. In the absence of rigorous analysis, previous scholarship posited that the didrachms were struck on the basis of two weigh standards, an Attic standard of c. 8.4 grams and a local, or Indian standard of c. 7.0 grams.³⁰ The weight distributions of the three components that comprise the didrachm sample (Series 1, 2 and 8) are coincident. Series 2 and 8 dominate the sample with no statistically significant variation between these components, which present a strongly unimodal distribution with a pronounced modal peak in the range 8.00-8.09 grams (Figure 4). The mean and median weights of the weight distribution (Table 2) fall within the modal class. On this basis it is interpreted that the weight target to which the didrachms were

²⁷ This weight adjustment discounts a fourth century BC origin for the imitative owls. Preceding and immediately after Alexander the Great's conquest of the east the Attic standard tetradrachm was 17.2 grams. Mørkholm (1991): 8-10 and 42; Hoover (2009): lxiv for the decrease in this weight standard through time in the Seleukid realm.

²⁸ Hoover (2009): lxiv; Houghton (2004): 59, table IV.

²⁹ Taylor (2019): 66-75 and figure 1.

³⁰ Hoover (2013): 3-6; Bopearachchi (1996); Bopearachchi (1998).

adjusted was 8.10 ± 0.10 grams. This represents a five percent seigniorage relative to the nominal Attic weight standard for the denomination derived from the tetradrachm (Table 3). Based on a sample of only 38 didrachms, the original metrological study suggested a target weight of 7.90 grams. The almost six-fold increase in the sample of didrachms has provided a far more representative sample of didrachm weights, due in large part to the relatively high percentage of unworn coins in recent commerce. It is most noteworthy that the lowest weights in the didrachm sample barely encompasses the so-called Indian weight standard (7.0 grams), while only a single coin achieves the weight of 8.4 grams that was hypothesized to be Attic weight standard for the didrachm. The weight range and the strongly unimodal character of the weight distribution invalidate the notion that the didrachm was adjusted on two weight standards.

The drachm sample is dominated by Series 3 (Athena/eagle) and Series 8 (Sophytes head/cockerel) with minor numbers of Series 1 and 2 (Athena/owl) and Series 10 (Athena/eagle). The weight distributions of component series overlies each other to present a well-developed modal class in the range 3.50-3.59 grams (Figure 5). This is very closely aligned with the mean and median of the distribution (Table 2). The estimated weight target to which the drachms were adjusted is 3.60 ± 0.05 grams. It matches the centre of the range of possibilities estimated in the original study, which was based on a sample one third the size of that now available. As with the didrachms, the weight distribution of the drachms is unimodal, indicative of a single weight standard. Seigniorage attached to the drachm is fifteen percent measured against the nominal Attic weight standard for the drachm derived from the tetradrachm (Table 3). Noteworthy is the fact that the weight adjustment of the drachm is higher than that of the Magadha-Mauryan *karshapana* (3.42 grams). Nor does the drachm weight adjustment correspond to either of the two or three *shana* denominations (2.91 grams and 4.37 grams respectively) in the Gandharan *shatamana* system that prevailed in northwest India in the Achaemenid period. This is contrary to the notion that the weight adjustment of the drachm was based on the Indian weight standard of coinage circulating in northwest India in the late 4th to early 3rd century BC. Conclusively, we can say that the drachms were not adjusted to an Indian weight standard, either in the 4th, or the 3rd centuries BC.

Numerically hemidrachms account for nine percent of the total sample. The hemidrachm assemblage is dominated by Series 2 (Athena/owl) and Series 3 (Athena/eagle) accompanied by lesser numbers of Series 1 (Athena/owl) and Series 8 (Sophytes head/cockerel). The distributions of weights in the component series are coincident (Figure 6), with a modal peak in the range 1.60-1.69 grams, while the next weight division, 1.70-1.79 grams contains only one less coin. The mean and median weights (Table 2) fall within the latter. This suggests that the weight adjustment of the hemidrachm denomination was 1.80 ± 0.10 grams, representing an adjustment with fifteen percent seigniorage when measured against the nominal Attic weight standard (Table 3). This weight adjustment is 0.10 grams higher than determined in the original study, which was based on a sample less than half the size of that now available.

In total, the small fractional denominations of diobol, trihemiobol and obol constitute only ten percent of the sample. The weight distributions of the component series represented in each fractional denomination are concomitant (Table 1). Each fraction displays a modal class. However, the mode of each of the diobol and trihemiobol is only marginally more frequent than the next highest weight division in each (Figure 7). With consideration of this, the weight adjustment of the

small fractions is estimated to be a diobol of 1.20 ± 0.05 grams, a trihemiobol of 0.90 ± 0.05 grams and diobol of 0.60 ± 0.05 grams. These weight estimates are slightly heavier than weight adjustment noted in the original study, which was based on less than half the data in the current sample. Based on the larger sample of the fractions, it now appears that the small fractions were each weight adjusted, like the drachms and hemidrachms, with a constant fifteen percent seigniorage relative to the nominal Attic weight standard for each denomination (Table 3). This is a significant insight, for the 2019 study suggested the possibility of a progressively increasing, rather than constant weight deficit in the smaller fractions.

Of necessity the small denominations were weight adjusted with higher precision than the larger denominations; a fact demonstrated by the significantly reduced standard deviation of each of the fractional coinage weight distributions compared to that of the larger denominations (Table 2). Absent such precision, the weight differentiation between the various classes of small fractions would have been lost. Precision in weight adjustment is a labour-intensive process. Therefore, we might anticipate that seigniorage, expressed as a percentage of the face value, to be a maximum in the smaller denominations.³¹ Such is indeed the case, reflected in a weight shortfall of fifteen percent measured against the nominal weight standard in each of the drachm, hemidrachm, diobol and obol denominations (Table 3).

Table 3. Weight adjustment for each denomination versus nominal Attic weight standard.

Denomination	Mean weight (g)	Weight adjustment (g)	Nominal weight standard (g)	Difference %
Tetradrachm	16.85	16.90 ± 0.10	17.00	-0.6
Didrachm	8.00	8.10 ± 0.10	8.50	-5
Drachm	3.57	3.60 ± 0.10	4.25	-15
Hemidrachm	1.71	1.80 ± 0.10	2.13	-15
Diobol	1.09	1.20 ± 0.05	1.40	-15
Trihemiobol	0.75	0.90 ± 0.50	1.05	-15
Obol	0.53	0.60 ± 0.05	0.71	-15

We are left with the question; why was this system of weight adjustment adopted? The answer must lie in the benefits that accrued to the issuing authority of an unofficial coinage. Firstly, it enabled the full cost of the coinage and perhaps even profit to be recovered from a mintage. For example, if the cost of striking the tetradrachm amounted to the equivalent of half of one percent of the face value, or 0.08 grams of silver, then at least this amount of silver would need to be recovered from each smaller denomination coins to cover costs.³² Thus, the percentage seigniorage involved would increase with smaller denominations. For the obol this would amount to a thirteen-percent weight deficit relative

³¹ Seigniorage was sought to cover the labour and general operating costs of the mint, and at a sufficiently high level might even generate a profit to the minting authority.

³² In fact, more than this would be involved given the required higher precision of weight adjustment and thus greater cost of adjusting and striking small denominations. The higher cost of issuing small denomination precious metal coinage and its adverse economic consequences have been demonstrated by Sargent and Velde (1999 and 2003) in an analysis of the coinages of Western Europe from 1300 to 1850. The same issue would have prevailed in ancient times.

to that of the nominal weight standard; close to that observed in the metrological analysis. The full recovery, or better, of the costs of a mintage would have been desirable in the absence of Seleukid treasury support. Another advantage of the substantial weight deficit in the adjustment of the small denominations is that this provided a disincentive to the circulation of coinage beyond the boundaries of the province, into the broader Seleukid domain where a heavier silver weight prevailed in the smaller denominations. From this aspect it is a reasonable surmise that the small denomination emissions, with their unique iconography, constituted an epichoric coinage directed to the local economy. Additionally, high seigniorage discouraged the removal from circulation of the smaller denomination coins, either as a store of value, or to melt for their silver content. This reduced the requirement for the mintage of costly fractions, the coinage of everyday transactions. In a closed epichoric currency system 'the state could over-value its own coins, assigning them a value higher than their real bullion content; it could also charge a premium for the exchange or reminting of foreign currency,'³³ thus generating a profit for the state.³⁴

In summary, the much-enlarged sample of the coinage of Andragoras and Sophytes permits a more robust metrological analysis, one that refines the estimates of the previously interpreted weight target to which each denomination was adjusted (Table 3). It indicates that the nominal weight standard employed was that of a reduced Attic tetradrachm of 17.00 grams with an increased fiduciary component of value (seigniorage) attached to the smaller denominations commencing with the didrachm. The data invalidate the notion that the didrachms and drachms were struck on two separate weight standards. Furthermore, each denomination was adjusted to its target weight in a consistent manner across all of the series of issues in each denomination. This is congruent with the findings established from the progression of shared mint controls, common elements of coin fabric and iconography that all eleven series comprise a single coinage system.³⁵

It is now possible to appreciate the overall context and structure of the system of weight adjustment against the nominal weight standard to which the coinage was struck. The nominal Attic weight standard tetradrachm of 17.00 grams prevailed throughout the Seleukid empire in the 3rd century BC. Conforming to this norm, the tetradrachm mintage could have served for military and mercenary payments, as well as being acceptable in the context of inter-regional trade settlements. In contrast, the smaller denominations depart appreciably from the nominal weight standard by virtue of substantial seigniorage approximating fifteen percent of the face value of the coin for the drachm and fractions. Due to the weight deficit, the coins of the small denominations would have been less acceptable outside the province of mintage. They most probably constituted an epichoric coinage system, which served a recipient base that accepted a substantially increased component of fiduciary value in the smaller denomination coinage. This component of the coinage must have served to facilitate transactions in a

³³ Thonemann (2015): 119.

³⁴ Ibid: 55 and 112-127 notes that closed epichoric currency systems were implemented with some frequency from the early years of the 3rd century BC and that these frequently served as part of a dual currency system; one component based on the international Attic standard for 'vertical' transactions with other Hellenistic royal states, and another, the epichoric component on a lighter weight standard for 'horizontal' transactions within and between cities in an epichoric currency union. Examples include that of Byzantium and Chalcedon in the second half of the 3rd century BC and the many *poleis* in western Asia Minor. The closed epichoric currency system introduced in Egypt by Ptolemy commencing 305 BC, fully implemented in 295 BC (Lorber 2018), set a precedent for the development of epichoric currency reforms throughout the former Macedonian empire in the 3rd century BC.

³⁵ Taylor (2019).

developing monetized economy of some scale; a distinctly broader purpose than military finance.³⁶ This approach is consistent with a 3rd century BC phenomenon outlined by Thonemann³⁷ whereby many Greek states implemented dual currency systems; one component conforming to the international Attic standard for 'vertical' transactions with other Hellenistic royal states, and another, the epichoric component, of a lighter weight for 'horizontal' transactions within and between cities in an epichoric currency union.

Strengthening this interpretation is a feature of the coinage system overlooked in previous scholarship, that of the relative prominence of the didrachm. Numerically didrachms constitute almost a quarter of the sample of the coinage, comparable in number to the drachms, second only to the tetradrachms which constitute one third of the sample. This relative significance is confirmed by the number of didrachms dies identified in a die study of the coinage.³⁸ The prominence of the didrachm is atypical of other Hellenistic eastern coinages of the 3rd century BC in which the didrachm is for the most part completely absent. It must reflect a local preference and use for this denomination, a further indication of the epichoric nature of this and the smaller denomination components of the currency system.

In this respect it is instructive to compare the Andragoras and Sophytes silver currency system to two of the easternmost Hellenistic coinages for which we have metrological data sets (Table 4). This comparison highlights the unique character of the coinage system compared to others for which we have metrological studies. It also illustrates the point that experimentation in coinage systems commenced in the Seleukid east in the first quarter of the third century BC with the departure of the Baktrian Seleukid coregency coinage from the Attic weight standard that was the legacy of Alexander the Great.³⁹

Table 4. Comparative metrology.

	Seleukid Coregency c. 285-281 BC		Andragoras- Sophytes c. 250s-238 BC		Euthydemos I c. 225-200 BC	
	Weight adjustment (g)	Nominal Standard (g)	Weight adjustment (g)	Nominal Standard (g)	Weight adjustment (g)	Nominal Standard (g)
Tetradrachm	13.80	14.00	16.90	17.00	16.55	16.60
Didrachm	-	-	8.10	8.50	-	-
Drachm	3.40	3.50	3.60	4.25	4.05	4.15
Hemidrachm	1.70	1.75	1.80	2.13	1.70	2.08
Diobol	-	-	1.20	1.40	-	-
Trihemiobol	-	-	0.90	1.05	-	-
Obol	0.55	0.58	0.60	0.71	0.60	0.69
Hemiobol	-	-	-	-	0.30	0.35

³⁶ Coming seventy years after Alexander the Great this should not be a surprise given the magnitude of Greek migration to the east in the intervening period and the resultant development of a more vibrant newly monetising economy. Alexander the Great coined primarily for military purposes. Almost a century later the structure, demographics and economy of the east had been transformed. We see this evidenced in the diversity of coinage in the east in the second half of the third century BC including an array of imitative coinages on the frontier of the former Macedonian empire.

³⁷ Thonemann (2015): 50 and 121-127.

³⁸ Taylor (2019): 64-66.

³⁹ Taylor (in prep).

The comparison addresses a number of interpretational errors that have frustrated past scholarship. Since the publication of Newell's *Eastern Seleucid Mints* numismatists have asserted that weight standard of the Sophytes drachm was the precursor to the light weight standard silver coinage struck in Bactria in the joint names of Seleukos and Antiochos, bearing the legend ΒΑΣΙΛΕΩΣ ΣΕΛΕΚΟΥ (ΚΑΙ) ΑΝΤΙΟΧΟΥ (SC 279-283). The drachm weight defining this standard was defined variously to be one that is less than 3.5 grams,⁴⁰ c. 3.5 grams,⁴¹ or 3.52 grams,⁴² and even as high as 3.75 grams.⁴³ Yet these varied propositions were unsupported by a metrological study. An analysis of a corpus of the coregency coinage⁴⁴ indicates that it was a traditionally scaled coinage system based on a nominal tetradrachm weight of 14.00 grams, from which the small denominations were scaled with the weight adjustment allowing for seigniorage of a few percent (Table 4). Clearly, this was a different weight standard and system of adjustment to that applied in the coinage of Sophytes. This overturns the proposition that the two coinages were struck on the same weight standard, and thus repudiates the hypothesis that the Sophytes coinage was the forerunner of the coregency issues. It breaks the frequently inferred chronological nexus between the two coinages.

Another comparable eastern coinage for which we have metrological data is that of Euthydemos I of Bactria (c. 225-200 BC).⁴⁵ This was based on a reduced Attic weight standard tetradrachm weight of 16.60 grams,⁴⁶ that appears to have been adopted by the Diodotid predecessors of Euthydemos.⁴⁷ After the treaty struck between the latter and Antiochos III in 206 BC, the weight standard was increased to 16.90 grams by the successors of Euthydemos,⁴⁸ closely conforming to that of the Seleukid realm. The silver coinage of Euthydemos, although struck on a lighter weight standard, displays a similar type of weight adjustment in the small denominations to that of Andragoras and Sophytes, with a comparable weight deficit of 10-18 percent for the drachm, hemidrachm, obol and hemiobol denominations relative to that of the nominal weight standard. Yet, no numismatist has deemed it necessary to invoke a second weight standard in the lesser denominations of the coinage system of Euthydemos in order to account for the shortfall in metal weight in the small denominations. This simply reflected the employment of a more aggressive seigniorage to cover the cost of mintage.

In the case of the coinage of Sophytes, the presumption of a second weight standard stemmed from the naive assumption that the coinage bearing the legend ΣΩΦΥΤΟΥ was struck by the Indian prince named Σωπειθης (Sopeithes) in the ancient sources who submitted to Alexander the Great.⁴⁹ *Ipso facto*, there followed the presumption that the first identified Sophytes drachm of 3.77 grams must have been struck on an 'Indian' weight standard. With circular reasoning, this presumption came to reinforce the identification of individual bearing the Greek name Sophytes

⁴⁰ Bopearachchi (1999): 79-80.

⁴¹ Houghton and Lorber (2002): 104.

⁴² Bordeaux (2021): 86.

⁴³ Newell (1938): 233.

⁴⁴ Taylor (in prep).

⁴⁵ Glenn (2020): 195-249. From this I have analysed the weights of coins in the smaller denominations to estimate the weight adjustment of the drachm and fractions to supplement Glenn's analysis of the tetradrachm weight adjustment. The results are summarized in Table 4.

⁴⁶ *Ibid*: 182.

⁴⁷ *Ibid*: 183-184, figure 55.

⁴⁸ *Ibid*: 182-185.

⁴⁹ Strabo *Geography* 15.1.30; Diodorus *Bibliotheca* 17.91-93; Arrian *Anabasis* 6.2.2.

(genitive ΣΩΦΥΤΟΥ) with the Indian dynast Sopeithes, and thus the transliteration of the name to Sophytes.⁵⁰ This manifestly circular reasoning was accepted to varying degrees for 150 years, without material evidence to support any of the propositions contained therein. Central to the maintenance of this circular reasoning was the mirage of an 'Indian' weight standard in the coinage, a mirage that still persists in recent scholarship,⁵¹ despite abundant evidence to the contrary.⁵²

To some extent this is understandable given the evolution of numismatic metrological study in the last century, succinctly summarised by Otto Mørkholm, for it is only relatively recently that attention has focussed on the empirical evaluation of the coin weights themselves:

The study of ancient weight standards used for striking coins was long dominated by the quest for a common origin of the various standards. This was usually located in Babylonia, and the most complicated arithmetical exercises, leading to quite arbitrary results, were preferred in order to derive the different theoretical norm weights from the light or heavy Babylonian *mina*. This highly speculative field of research subsequently came under attack from more pragmatic scholars who preferred to concentrate on the actual weights. Although the pan-Babylonian ghost shows a tendency to reappear at intervals, the pragmatic attitude may now be said to dominate the study of ancient metrology.⁵³

Based on empirical analysis, our new understanding of the coinage system of Andragoras and Sophytes comes more than 150 years after the first published record of the Sophytes drachm,⁵⁴ which was the origin of an erroneous numismatic assumption, that of the existence of an 'Indian' weight standard in the coinage. This evolved into a pedagogical dogma, despite strong arguments to the contrary,⁵⁵ and was even extended beyond its original application to encompass the proposition that two weight standards applied simultaneously in and across various denominations of the coinage. This occurred in the absence of coherent metrological analysis to support the proposition. Yet the metrological data available for the last thirty years, now swelled by the data from the so called Andragoras-Sophytes Group in commerce,⁵⁶ provides strong evidence to the contrary. From the last decade of the twentieth century, it appears that the systematic gathering and analysis of the relevant metrological data was subordinated to pre-existing assumptions, a dynamic that pervades many disciplines; the manifestation of a collective cognitive dissonance anchored in an outdated hypothesis that is invalidated by new data. The Nobel laureate physicist Max Planck remarked on this phenomenon and its role in stifling the advancement of knowledge; 'A new scientific truth does

⁵⁰ Cunningham (1866). The name Sophytes was derived from Cunningham's desire to equate the legend ΣΩΦΥΤΟΥ with the individual named Σοπειθης (Sopeithes) in the ancient sources, which as noted by Whitehead (1943): 63-65 was a false etymology. Certainly, Sophytos is the correct name, also attested to a 1st century BC stele found in Kandahar naming a successful merchant or trader σωφΥΤοc (Sophytos spelled with a lunate sigma); Bernard et al (2004).

⁵¹ Bordeaux (2021); Jansari (2019).

⁵² Taylor (2021).

⁵³ Mørkholm (1991): 7. Refer to Raymond (1953): 18-42 for an example of the complicated arithmetical exercises undertaken in a metrological evaluation of Macedonian regal coinage of the 6th-5th centuries BC that promulgated the concept of a Thraco-Macedonian weight standard, a complex two-tiered weight system derived from both the heavy and light Babylonian *mina*. This was rejected in more recent studies; Kagan (2006): 53-54; Wartenberg (2015): 351-352; Psoma (2015): 169-171. Jansari (2018): 85-86 offers a recent example of the resurrection of the 'pan-Babylonian ghost' applied to the Sophytes coinage in justification of an Indian origin for the coinage.

⁵⁴ Cunningham (1866).

⁵⁵ Whitehead (1943): 62; Rapson (1922): 61, 388, and 462-3.

⁵⁶ Roma Numismatics (2017): 106.

not triumph by convincing its opponents and making them see the light, but rather because its opponents eventually die, and a new generation grows up that is familiar with it.⁵⁷

Encouragingly in this respect, the distinguished scholar of Asian numismatics, Joe Cribb has noted that 'It is certain that our past understandings of both Sophytes and Andragoras need to be reassessed. Like you I think data should lead the discussion, not vague references in classical texts and past opinion.'⁵⁸ Definitely, the metrological analysis proves the point for it has categorically dispersed the mirage of an 'Indian' weight standard in the coinage of Sophytes.

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Series 1: Tetradrachm - Roma Numismatics XIV, 344. www.romanumismatics.com.

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Series 3: Drachm - Roma Numismatics XX, 328.

Series 4: Diobol - Roma Numismatics XIV, 339.

Series 5: Obol - Triton XIV, 409.

Series 6: Tetradrachm - Roma Numismatics XIV, 327.

Series 7: Tetradrachm - Roma Numismatics XIV, 364.

Series 7: Diobol - Noble Numismatics 127, 4336; CNG 69, 779.

Series 8: Tetradrachm - Roma Numismatics XV, 348.

Series 9: Trihemiobol - CNG 103, 461. www.cngcoins.com.

Series 10: Drachm - BM 1882,0703.1.

Series 11: Trihemiobol - Elsen 94, 43.

⁵⁷ Planck (1950): 33-34.

⁵⁸ In email correspondence with Joe Cribb (19 August 2021).

SOPHYTES AND THE MIRAGE OF AN 'INDIAN' WEIGHT STANDARD

Figure 3. Histograms: tetradrachm weights.

Figure 4. Histograms: didrachm weights.

SOPHYTES AND THE MIRAGE OF AN 'INDIAN' WEIGHT STANDARD

Figure 5. Histograms: drachm weights.

Figure 6. Histograms: hemidrachm weights.

SOPHYTES AND THE MIRAGE OF AN 'INDIAN' WEIGHT STANDARD

Figure 7. Histograms: small fraction weights.

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